

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

Yopa Serges¹, Kuete Merlin², Koulayom Henri³

¹Advanced School of Economics and Commerce, University of Douala, Cameroon.

^{2,3}Faculty of Economics and management, University of Bangui, Central Republic of Africa.

ABSTRACT: In recent decades, the incorporation of sustainable development principles into marketing has increased significantly. Consequently, researchers have explored the contrasting relationships between the two areas to evaluate their respective relevance. In response to this change, researchers and practitioners have explored the possibilities of incorporating sustainability concepts into marketing. Therefore, the aim of this study is to focus on the cultural and political factors that explain the development of sustainable marketing in Cameroonian industrial enterprises in light of the existing literature on sustainability and marketing. To achieve this goal, we collected qualitative and quantitative primary and secondary data from a sample of 74 Cameroonian industrial enterprises in the Centre, Littoral and West regions. We used different statistical tools such as descriptive, exploratory, correlation and explanatory analysis. The results of this approach show that cultural and political factors such as human resource development, religion, language, ethnicity, compliance with laws and regulations, adherence to standards, and quality explain the implementation of sustainable marketing in industrial enterprises in Cameroon. Therefore, we recommend that public and private organisations strengthen their environmental discourse, especially in developing countries, in order to successfully transition to more responsible practices.

KEYWORDS: Sustainable development, cultural and political factors, sustainable marketing.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the incorporation of sustainable development principles into business practices has not only gained momentum but has become a key aspect of corporate strategies across a range of sectors [Ahmed et al., 2020; Ahmad et al., 2021]. This is primarily due to growing awareness of pressing environmental and social issues such as climate change, resource depletion, and social inequality, which has brought sustainable development to the forefront of global concerns [Kilbourne, 2006; Reisinger, 2015; Kemper and Hall, 2019]. Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic and the political crisis between Russia and Ukraine have pushed stakeholders to place sustainability at the center of the global discussion, leading many companies and organisations to develop sustainable frameworks to address key environmental issues to address social and financial issues (Kemper et al., 2019). In these uncertain times, marketers and practitioners are realising the importance of sustainability in all industries [Çankaya and Sezen, 2016; Lim, 2016; Ahmad et al., 2021].

Thus, companies are being held increasingly accountable not only for their economic performance but also for their impact on society and the environment. Companies are under pressure to implement systematic changes and adopt sustainable approaches in response to market trends [Kumar, 2016; Kim et al., 2018]. In response to these pressures, sustainable marketing has become a key focus, reflecting the need for companies to align their marketing strategies with broader sustainability goals (Jung, Y.J. & Kim, Y., 2023). This approach goes beyond traditional marketing by integrating environmental and social considerations into all aspects of the marketing mix, from product development to communication strategies, with the goal of promoting not only profitability but also long-term social welfare.

This trend towards sustainable marketing has sparked great interest among both researchers and practitioners keen to explore how

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

sustainability principles can be effectively incorporated into marketing practice [Lin et al., 2012; Reisinger, 2015; Lim, 2016; Kim, 2018; Lunde, 2018; and Afshari et al., 2022]. The challenge is to find ways to increase environmental responsibility while promoting business success. This dual goal requires companies to rethink their marketing strategies and adopt approaches that prioritise ethical consumption, reduce environmental impact, and promote a positive social legacy [Lee and Kim, 2022; Afshari et al., 2022; Font and McCabe, 2017; Lee et al., 2022; Sizai, 2021]. However, the successful implementation of sustainable marketing is not uniform across all geographies and is strongly influenced by the cultural, political, and socio-economic contexts in which companies operate. Therefore, understanding these contextual factors is essential to developing effective and culturally appropriate sustainable marketing strategies. According to the work of Kotler (1972), van Dam and Apeldoorn (1996), Aaker (1996), Kotler (2011), and Eccles and Serafeim (2013), the relationship between sustainability and marketing is complex and multifaceted in nature, a delicate balance between ethical considerations and business goals. Sustainability advocates for long-term environmental stewardship and social responsibility, whereas traditional marketing is often associated with short-term profitability and consumer satisfaction [Jones et al., 2008; Reisinger, 2015]. These seemingly different goals can cause tensions within organisations that attempt to achieve immediate business goals while engaging in sustainable practices. Integrating sustainability into marketing requires a nuanced approach that **acknowledges** these challenges and **attempts** to reconcile them [Leisinger, 2015; Font and McCabe, 2017; D'Souza et al., 2019]. This approach must take into account the unique cultural and political factors that shape marketing practices in different regions, and recognize that what works in one context may not be applicable in another. Research on sustainable marketing practices has received particular attention in recent years. Studies have explored consumer expectations and business strategies related to sustainability (Trivedi et al., 2018), as well as the challenges of implementing sustainable policies into market practices (Mattsson, 2016). The fashion industry in particular has been a focus of sustainable market research, with researchers investigating consumer behavior, purchase intentions, and attitudinal and behavioral gaps in sustainable fashion consumption (Ray & Nayak, 2023). In the luxury sector, sustainable market research has addressed consumer and organisational concerns as well as international and cross-cultural issues (Athwal et al., 2019). However, gaps remain in understanding how sustainable fashion can benefit from B2B marketing, circular economy principles, and sustainability-focused innovation, especially in emerging markets (Ray & Nayak, 2023). She also argues for broader, deeper, and more critical research into the relationship between sustainability and luxury (Athwal et al., 2019).

Cameroon, a developing country, is no exception to the global trend toward sustainable development in the industrial sector. Cameroonian businesses face economic, social, and environmental challenges that require deep consideration in integrating sustainable marketing into their business practices [Oginni & Omojowo, 2015; Mbiajo & Djumene, 2015]. In particular, it is important to understand the cultural and political factors that influence sustainable marketing. These factors range from local beliefs and traditions to environmental regulations and governance structures, all of which influence how sustainability is perceived and implemented. With increasing awareness of the importance of environmental and social sustainability around the world, the application of sustainable marketing in Cameroonian businesses has become a critical issue. Cameroonian businesses would benefit from integrating sustainable marketing practices into their operations to meet the expectations of sustainability-conscious consumers and contribute to the country's sustainable development. Literature on sustainable marketing practices in Cameroon reveals several key factors. The adoption of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) among Cameroonian SMEs is influenced by factors such as financial resources, institutional environment, firm size, and business ethics (Ben Boubakary et al., 2024). Cultural diversity also plays a role in firm sustainability, with ethnic and linguistic diversity generally having a positive impact, while religious diversity has a negative impact (Tagne & Evou, 2020). The adoption of sustainable business models in Cameroonian industries is still in its early stages, indicating the need for a more holistic approach to sustainability (Oginni & Omojowo, 2015). In mobile marketing, factors influencing adoption include perceived benefits, partner influence, and traditional communication methods (Mbiadjo and Djumene, 2015). These studies reveal the complex interplay of cultural, organisational, and environmental factors that shape sustainable marketing practices in Cameroon. Although the existing literature refers to the integration of sustainability into marketing (Mattsson (2016); Trivedi et al. (2018); Athwal et al. (2019) and Ray & Nayak (2023)), cultural and political factors influence the development and implementation of sustainable marketing practices in industrial enterprises in developing countries, especially in the Cameroonian context. Existing studies have also explored the role played by specific cultural elements such as community responsibility, religion, language and ethnicity. The role of diversity in developing sustainable marketing strategies has not been sufficiently explored. This study aims to fill this gap by analysing how these cultural and political factors determine the implementation of sustainable marketing strategies in industrial enterprises in Cameroon, thereby improving our understanding of the specific cultural and political drivers of sustainable

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

marketing. These insights may not only be applicable to other developing countries with similar challenges but also enhance their competitiveness in a rapidly evolving global market. In the remainder of this paper, we divide the work into three main parts. First, we present the literature review (I) and explain the methodology (II). Then, we present the results of the descriptive, exploratory and correlation analyses and finally discuss the results of the descriptive analysis (III).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

We start with a review of the theoretical literature (I.1), followed by an empirical study (I.2) linking the development of sustainable marketing to cultural and political determinants.

2.1 Ecomarketing in organisations: the theoretical background

Several theories and concepts establish the relationship between cultural and political factors and sustainable marketing. These connections are often complex and vary depending on the historical, geographical and economic context. These include the theory of cultural values; social identity theory; neo-institutional theory; stakeholder theory; reformist theory and transformist theory. According to Hofstede (1980), the theory of cultural values is one of the most influential contributions to understanding cultural differences in organizations. Hofstede identified several cultural dimensions that allow analysing how cultural values affect the behavior of individuals and organisations around the world. These dimensions include hierarchical distance, individualism and collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, masculinity and femininity, long-term and short-term orientation, patience and restraint. However, it has been widely criticised, especially for its simplification of national cultures. In fact, cultural values theory is based on a static view of culture and ignores cultural development over time. This study uses cultural value theory to understand how these aspects affect the adoption of sustainable practices. Thus, the analysis of cultural aspects in the Cameroonian context helps explain the differences in companies' commitment to sustainable marketing. According to H. Tajfel (1972), social identity theory investigates how social group membership affects individuals' attitudes and behaviors. According to this theory, individuals categorise themselves and others according to their membership in various social groups, such as ethnicity, religion, and language.

This categorisation creates a sense of belonging and solidarity within a group as well as a sense of otherness among other groups. Thus, individuals' actions are often aimed at promoting and defending the interests of the group to which they belong. Although the theory is influential, it also has critics. One of the main criticisms is that it tends to simplify complex identity dynamics by reducing individuals to passive members of social groups. This simplification can ignore the diversity of identities that individuals hold and the circumstances in which some identities are more salient than others. In the context of industrial enterprises in Cameroon, social identity theory helps understand how affiliation to ethnic, religious, or linguistic groups influences the adoption of sustainable marketing practices. Thus, the social identities of the owners/managers and employees play a key role in the implementation of sustainable marketing.

Paul DiMaggio and Walter Powell's neo-institutional theory (1983) investigates how organisational structures and practices are influenced by institutional pressures. According to this theory, organisations adopt practices not only for reasons of economic efficiency but also to conform to the normative, cultural, and legal expectations of the organisational environment. DiMaggio and Powell identify three types of intra-organisational pressures that lead to the homogenisation of organisational practices: coercive pressures (legal and regulatory pressures), mimetic pressures (imitation of the practices of other organisations that are perceived to be legitimate), and normative pressures (pressures from experts and social norms). However, it has been criticised for its institutional determinism, which suggests that organisations are essentially shaped by external pressures, leaving little room for innovation or resistance. Moreover, neo-institutional theory tends to overemphasise organisational homogeneity as a result of institutional isomorphism (coercive, mimetic, normative) and downplay differences between organisations within the same institutional environment. In the context of sustainable marketing in Cameroon, neo-institutional theory can be applied to explain how industrial companies are affected by environmental regulations, quality standards (as defined by ANOR), and cultural and societal expectations for sustainability. This perspective allows us to understand the external forces that encourage companies to incorporate sustainable marketing into their strategies.

Stakeholder theory, proposed by R. E. Freeman (1984), is an approach that extends the traditional framework of corporate governance by suggesting that corporations must not only satisfy shareholders but also consider the interests of all stakeholders involved in or affected by their activities. These stakeholders include customers, employees, suppliers, local communities, governments, and NGOs.

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

The theory also posits that a corporation's long-term success depends on its ability to balance the diverse interests of stakeholders by integrating responsible and sustainable practices into corporate operations. Although the theory has been praised for its integrative approach, it is not immune to criticism.

One of the most common criticisms is that the theory remains prescriptive, requiring companies to consider the interests of all stakeholders, and does not provide clear guidelines for dealing with conflicts of interest between these different parties. This ambiguity can create real challenges for companies, which often have to mediate between competing stakeholder demands. In the context of sustainable marketing in industrial companies in Cameroon, stakeholder theory suggests that companies must meet the growing sustainability expectations of their stakeholders. For example, consumers may demand environmentally friendly products, while employees may want to work for companies that adhere to ethical standards. Local governments can impose strict environmental regulations, and communities can expect companies to contribute to the sustainable development of their region. Incorporating these expectations into marketing strategies allows companies to improve their reputation and stakeholder relations, as well as strengthen their market position as responsible actors. This approach emphasises the importance of multi-stakeholder engagement in implementing sustainable marketing, especially in culturally and politically complex contexts such as Cameroon. Reform theory, also known as the incremental, instrumental or evolutionary approach, is a theoretical current characterised by a tendency to uphold existing ideologies, structures and beliefs without seeking to fundamentally change the functioning of the existing system (Merizrow, 2004; Glisczinski, 2007; Blasco, 2012). This current supports innovation as a means to gain competitive advantage and improve corporate performance within a capitalist or green growth framework. The innovations advocated are often strategic, decision-making, or managerial in nature, aiming to facilitate the use of management or management tools. This approach is expressed in the search for "win-win" solutions where each party finds its interests (Stubbs and Cocklin, 2008). This trend is generally recognised as reformist, characterised by business acumen, which promotes the integration of environmental principles while maintaining organisational performance characterised by effectiveness and efficiency. The transformist approach is characterised by a determination to break with established models to integrate the principles of sustainable development or sustainable marketing, and it categorically rejects the current paradigm based on market laws or growth principles (Marshall et al., 2010). The stakeholder theory proposed by R. E. Freeman (1984) is an approach that extends the traditional framework of corporate governance by suggesting that a company must not only satisfy its shareholders but also take into account the interests of all stakeholders involved in the company's activities that are involved or affected by them. These stakeholders include customers, employees, suppliers, local communities, governments, and NGOs. The theory also posits that a company's long-term success depends on its ability to balance the diverse interests of its stakeholders by integrating responsible and sustainable practices into its operations. Having presented the theoretical approach above, it is appropriate to consider in more detail the research that has been carried out in this field.

2.2. Determinants of sustainable marketing development: An empirical study

A comprehensive literature review highlights the crucial importance of implementing sustainable marketing in companies, especially in the industrial sector. Since the 1970s, ecology has been recognised as one of the key criteria in strategic decision-making processes (Marguerat and Cestre, 2002).

2.2.1. Perspectives on Green Marketing Development

In the late 1960s and early 1970s marketing literature, there was critical reflection and discussion of the role of marketing in the process of social and environmental change (Kelley 1971; Anderson and Cunningham 1972; Fisk 1974). In fact, the increasing number of laws, the rise of environmental protection organizations, and the development of a consumer society gradually increased the interest of companies and the media. At that time, environmental concerns were gradually being integrated into management and marketing education and practice, as evidenced by seminal works such as Henion (1976), Kinnear and Taylor (1973), and Kinnear et al. (1973). (1974), cited in Marguerat and Cestre (2002). Although consumers seem to be becoming more aware of climate change, some authors, notably Swim et al. (2009), have noted their inaction. According to Stamm et al. (2000, cited in Bérubé, 2010), the main cause of this inaction is the lack of understanding of the real causes and effects of climate change, which leads consumers to delay taking action. However, it should be noted that there is very little research on this topic, as Swim et al. (2009) point out. For some authors, this introspection also included the ethical and social problematization of marketing as an organisation and calls for commercial organisations to assume more responsibility in society as corporate citizens (Dawson 1971; Lazer 1969; Lazer and Kelley 1973). For example, Kelley (1971) argued that marketers should shift their focus from "satisfying individual needs" to "social

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Politic Context

considerations." Dawson (1971) and Kotler (1972) argued that it was important to recognise that this growing concern for consumer welfare went far beyond mere customer dissatisfaction with a product that was perceived to be inferior.

2.2.2. From Social Marketing to Ecological Marketing

Although social marketing primarily addressed consumer concerns, the demands of environmental activists were taken up by other marketers who recognised that environmental issues required significant changes in the marketing field, including educating consumers and marketers about the relationship between their everyday choices and the natural environment (Feldman 1971; Fisk 1973, 1974). In this regard, Fisk (1973, 1974) made an important contribution by proposing the theory of responsible consumption and the imperative to protect the environment, which emphasises the responsibility of marketers in limiting personal consumption. From this perspective, an important social goal of marketing is to promote responsible and non-frivolous consumption by engaging consumers as responsible and informed market participants.

In another effort to provide new solutions to environmental problems, Henion and Kinnear (1976) introduced ecological marketing, which concerns all marketing activities: (1) activities that have contributed to causing environmental problems, and (2) activities that can be used to provide a remedy for environmental problems.

Despite an initial boom in contributions in the 1970s, discussions of marketing's responsibility towards the environment and society faded somewhat and this new field of marketing was relegated to the annals of marketing history (Mintu and Lozada, 1993; Mohd and Mohd, 2015). It has been suggested that the oil crises of 1973 and 1980, a strong belief in the ability of market mechanisms to redress environmental imbalances, and marketers' lack of interest in environmental and social issues prevented marketers from conducting new research in this area (Peattie, 1995; Sheth and Parvathyar, 1995; Mohd and Mohd, 2015). It was not until the late 1980s that environmental and social issues, in conjunction with renewed debates on the role of marketing in society, returned to the centre of public attention again and new concepts such as green marketing, environmental marketing and eco-entrepreneurial marketing were introduced. 1992; Coddington 1993; Peattie and Crane 2005; Varadarajan and Menon 1988). For example, Mintu and Lozada (1993) defined green marketing as the application of marketing concepts and tools to promote interactions that achieve organisational and individual goals in a way that preserves, protects, and sustains the physical environment. Unlike the green marketing concept, this approach prescribes a more proactive role for marketers to not only monitor the negative impacts of their marketing activities on the natural environment, but also to actively implement practices that reduce or minimize these impacts.

2.2.3. Sustainable marketing: challenges and future prospects

The development of sustainable marketing brings many benefits, but there are also challenges to overcome. As sustainable marketing has evolved from traditional marketing, these challenges are diverse and complex. McDonagh and Prothero (2014) highlight the tension between commercial and sustainability goals within companies and resistance to change by internal stakeholders. These challenges require effective management and thoughtful integration of sustainable marketing principles. Dechiri et al. (2023). Moreover, it should be noted that environmental marketing is recognised by some authors as an opportunity for commercial growth (Coddington, 1993). Note that the term "sustainable marketing" was first formally introduced in 1996 by Van Dam and Apeldoorn (1996). They emphasised the need to balance competitive marketing activities with an environmentally sustainable approach. From a macro-marketing perspective, they identified a key link between marketing and sustainable development and emphasised that a transition from traditional consumer marketing to a more sustainable model is essential. They argued that sustainability can only be truly achieved through a combination of active government intervention and marketing strategies focused on more environmentally friendly consumption and production models. Menon and Menon (1997) proposed the concept of "environmental entrepreneurial marketing," which describes the process of creating and implementing entrepreneurial marketing strategies focused on environmental benefits from a business perspective. These efforts aim to generate revenue by proposing exchanges that balance the economic and social performance objectives of the firm (see also Varadarajan, 1992).

However, in many discussions on the subject, sustainable marketing is often considered to be a logical extension of the traditional concept of managerial marketing (Crane and Desmond, 2002; Kilbourne, 1998). For example, Fuller (1999) redefined sustainable marketing as the process of planning, implementing and controlling the development, pricing, promotion and distribution of products with three imperatives: satisfying customer needs, achieving organisational goals, and ensuring compatibility with the ecosystem. This line of research is generally based on a micromarketing approach, which is managerial in nature, as opposed to a macromarketing perspective, which sees sustainable marketing from a more societal perspective. This development reveals that numerous theoretical and empirical studies concentrate on the shift from traditional marketing to sustainable marketing. This

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

development highlights the crucial importance of socio-economic factors as a tool to develop sustainable marketing (SM). The challenge is to successfully integrate these elements to ensure a marketing approach that is economically viable, environmentally sustainable and socially beneficial.

2.3. Cultural and Political Factors as Determinants of DSM

Research on sustainable marketing has highlighted the importance of cultural and political factors when companies develop sustainable marketing strategies. Furthermore, according to Patel et al. (2006), these are important factors in the lives of individuals in society and many failures in marketing are a direct result of a lack of sensitivity to and consideration of the cultural realities in which consumers find themselves. According to Bosson et al. (2016), companies should take into account consumers' values, beliefs, and cultural preferences to develop products and services that meet their needs and wants. Similarly, government laws and regulations and public policies also play an important role in motivating companies to adopt more sustainable practices (Manta et al., 2021). Following this research, numerous studies have also investigated the relationship between cultural and political factors and consumer behavior toward sustainable marketing. In this context, noteworthy is a study by Lima et al. (2024), which showed that consumers in a particular country are more likely to purchase sustainable products if they perceive their culture as placing importance on the environment and sustainability. Similarly, studies have shown that government policies that promote sustainable development can stimulate consumer demand for sustainable products and services (Gonzalez-Benito et al., 2022). In the specific context of Cameroon, cultural factors such as ethnic diversity, customs, and traditions can affect consumer perceptions of sustainable products and services. Companies therefore need to be aware of these cultural peculiarities to adapt their marketing strategies and communicate effectively with potential customers (Tagne & Evou, 2020). Furthermore, Cameroonian public policies and environmental regulations may play an important role in the adoption of sustainable practices by industrial companies (Alfoqahaa & Safi, 2015). Government incentives, such as tax breaks for companies that adopt sustainable practices, may encourage the integration of sustainable marketing into Cameroonian companies' business strategies. As we have now discovered, cultural and political factors not only determine consumer behavior, but can also influence companies' strategic decisions regarding sustainable marketing. In this regard, companies may choose to develop marketing campaigns specifically adapted to national or regional cultural values and preferences, which may be crucial to succeed in a particular market (Bašan et al., 2021). Likewise, companies may be encouraged to adopt sustainable practices depending on the environmental expectations and policies of local or international governments (Delmas and Pekovic, 2017). From all this, the following hypotheses are derived:

H₁: Cultural factors have a significant impact on the implementation of sustainable marketing in Cameroon's industrial sector companies.

H₂: Political factors have a significant impact on the implementation of sustainable marketing in Cameroon's industrial sector companies.

3. Data and empirical strategy

The aim of this study is to focus on the cultural and political factors that explain the implementation of sustainable marketing in industrial companies in Cameroon. This study's main hypothesis is that cultural and political factors, considered separately, have a significant impact on the development of sustainable marketing in industrial enterprises in Cameroon. To test this hypothesis, we apply logistic regression and the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression method. The model is given by the following equation:

$$DSM_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CP_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (3.1)$$

For the purposes of our study, an exploratory approach is used first, followed by descriptive and correlational analyses, and finally explanatory analyses. However, before outlining the steps of these different analyses, it is necessary to introduce the sample, variables, and econometric model used in this study. The different statistical tools used include descriptive statistics, constructing variables, operationalising variables, exploring variables using principal component analysis, and econometric modeling. Furthermore, this study is based on regression models applied to qualitative ordinal variables. The goal of this analysis is to present descriptive statistics highlighting the different variables in the model.

3.1 Study sample

The sample of our study consists of 74 companies from the industrial sector in Cameroon recorded in 2021. Data were obtained from both primary and secondary sources, such as semi-structured interviews and questionnaires filled out during face-to-face interviews.

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

The data are qualitative and quantitative. From the complete list of companies received from the National Institute of Statistics (INS) of Cameroon, we selected the industrial companies to be included in the study, regardless of their legal form, field of activity, or size. We selected companies engaged in the processing of raw materials and based in three Cameroonian cities: Yaoundé, Douala and Bafoussam. This choice is justified by the fact that these three cities host a large number of industrial companies, most of which have their management or headquarters in Douala, Bafoussam or Yaoundé.

3.2 Variable specification and econometric model

3.2.1. Variable specification

The aim is to present the operationalisation of the dependent variable and the selected independent variables. These variables are defined here using observable and measurable events, so-called indicators, so that they can be measured later.

Dependent variable: development of sustainable marketing (DSM) According to authors such as Van Dam and Apeldoorn (1996), Sempel and Vandercammen (2009) and Elsa de Gerus (2013), the questions to assess the knowledge and development level of sustainable marketing in industrial enterprises in Cameroon are: What is the level of sustainable marketing practice in your company? With this in mind, we used questions on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "1 – very low" to "5 – very high."

Independent variable: cultural and political factors As stated in the literature, cultural and political factors play an important role in the development of sustainable marketing. These factors are summarised in the table below:

Table 1: Cultural and political factors

independent Variables	items	sources
Cultural factors (Values and beliefs of the owner-manager) (CULTU)	As an owner-manager, your top priority is your personal development (C1)	Pin, Castro, Silva, Nani (2006), (Charter et al, 2002). Pastore-Reiss
	Is the application of sustainable marketing in your company explained by your belief in the usefulness of sustainable development? (C2)	
	The owner-manager's religion determines the implementation of sustainable marketing (C3)	
	The language of the owner-manager determines the implementation of sustainable marketing (C4)	
	The ethnicity of the owner-manager explains the level of implementation of sustainable marketing(C5)	
Political variables (standards and of legislation) (POLTQ))	Your products and/or services are subject to standards or laws on compliance with the principles of sustainable development (P1)	Gendron, 2005; Revéret et Turcotte 2009 ; Paradas (2006)
	Can you indicate whether these standards, laws or regulations are what prompted you to introduce sustainable development practices in your company? (P2)	
	your company's products comply with the standards and quality prescribed by ANOR (P3)	

Source: authors based on questionnaire

The cultural and political factors used in this article are based on studies by Imed Zaiem (2005), Oginni & Omojowo (2015), and Asamoah et al. (2017). According to the authors, cultural and political factors are likely to have a significant impact on businesses' adoption of sustainable marketing practices. In their analysis, the authors found a clear relationship between the development of sustainable marketing and the factors. Our study aims to focus on socio-economic determinants in the development of sustainable marketing. To do this, we test an econometric model defined as follows:

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

$$DSM_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CP + \epsilon_i \quad (3.1)$$

Thus, CP stands for all cultural and political factors ; DSM: state for sustainable marketing development. CP: cultural and political factors retained after exploratory analysis.

3.3. Applied estimation method

In our study, we have both dependent and independent variables. The dependent variables are measured using a 5-point Likert scale. Ordinal logistic regression is used to estimate the model using the maximum likelihood method. We then perform a least-squares linear regression to check the robustness of the results obtained previously.

4. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

The objective here is to present the behavior of industrial enterprises in Cameroon through the characteristics of the sample, the characteristics of the different enterprises and the determinants, in terms of sustainable marketing and development; a description of the elements of the exploratory analysis; and finally, a deeper analysis to make it more specific.

4.1. Results of the exploratory analysis

Now that the different theories have been presented, it is necessary to test them using data from the database. This section presents the results of the exploratory factor analysis (PCA) used to validate and build the scales measuring the cultural and political determinants of the DSM. Dependence and correlation tests are then analysed to reveal significant relationships between these factors and the implementation of sustainable marketing. These analyses are followed by the results of analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests to assess the importance of cultural and political factors. We also discuss the results of ordinal and multiple linear logistic regression models (Equation 3.1) to identify the key determinants of DSM. These analyses are followed by a discussion highlighting the differences and convergences with the existing literature. Finally, we conclude with a critical review of the consequences of these findings. Our findings show that there is a significant relationship between cultural and political factors and the development of sustainable marketing (SM) in industrial enterprises in Cameroon. More specifically, dependency tests show that factors such as personal fulfilment, belief in the usefulness of sustainable development, religion, language and ethnic group membership have a significant impact on the development of sustainable marketing. Similarly, political factors such as compliance with laws and regulations and respect for quality standards set by the Agency for Standards and Quality (ANOR) also play an important role in the adoption of sustainable marketing practices. Pearson correlation analysis confirms these observations, showing positive and significant relationships between DSM and several cultural factors with coefficients ranging from 0.326 to 0.706. Cultural factors such as self-actualisation, religion and language have high correlation coefficients, indicating that they have a strong relationship with the implementation of sustainable marketing. However, it is noteworthy that some political factors, especially obedience to laws and regulations (P1 and P2), do not show significant correlations. This suggests that their influence on DSM may be more complex or indirect. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests support these conclusions, showing that cultural and political factors have a significant impact on the level of sustainable marketing practices. All probabilities associated with Fisher statistics for these groups of factors are below the traditional significance thresholds (below the 10%, 5% and 1% thresholds), confirming the importance of these aspects in the development of sustainable marketing. These findings emphasize the interdependence of various areas that influence sustainable marketing practices, as well as the importance of a holistic approach in their analysis. Both ordinal logistic and multiple linear regression models were used to identify the main determinants of DSM. Personal fulfilment and language were found to be cultural factors positively and significantly associated with DSM, whereas religion had a significant negative relationship. In terms of policy, compliance with ANOR standards and quality has a positive and significant impact on DSM, whereas compliance with laws and standards has a negative impact. These results suggest that certain cultural and regulatory aspects may facilitate the development of sustainable marketing, while others may act as barriers. This perhaps reflects resistance or incompatibility with current business practices.

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

Table 2: Estimated relationship between cultural and political determinants and the development of sustainable marketing

Independent Variables	Logit ordinal	Linear Regression
C1 : Personal development	2.6211*** (0.000)	0.7362*** (0.000)
C2: Belief in the usefulness of sustainable development	0.0847 (0.753)	-0.011 (0.990)
C3 : Religion	-1.9043*** (0.000)	-0.3584*** (0.000)
C4 : Language	0.4815*** (0.000)	0.2959 (0.011)
C5: Membership of an ethnic group	0.0984 (0.404)	-0.214 (0.068)
P1: Compliance with laws or standards	0.8129** (0.044)	-0.1221*** (0.000)
P2: Products and/or services subject to regulation	2.9825*** (0.310)	0.6717 (0.615)
P3: Compliance with ANOR standards and quality	6.195*** (0.000)	1.1776*** (0.001)
Constant	0.829*** (0.002)	-3.8852*** (0.000)
PseudoR2/R2	0.4120	0.6535
R ² adjusted	0.4876	0.6224
Probability	0.0000	0.0000
LR chi2/Fcal	99.62	31.30
No. of observation	74	74

***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1. N =74; Source: Computed by author using SPSS V20

Ultimately, these results show elements of both convergence and divergence with the existing literature. Moreover, in contrast to the studies of Schwartz (2006) and Aka (2009), which highlight the importance of owner-managers' personal beliefs and values in adopting sustainable practices, our study found no significant relationship between owner-managers' beliefs and values. Sustainable development and the usefulness of DSM depend on managers' beliefs. Similarly, the ambiguous influence of political factors suggests that the mere presence of laws and standards is not enough to guarantee the adoption of sustainable practices, and their effectiveness may depend on their enforcement and acceptance by companies. These findings also highlight the complexity of the dynamics taking place in practice, indicating that a more nuanced and holistic approach is needed to understand the integration of sustainable marketing practices in industrial companies. Finally, these findings call for further consideration of incentive and regulatory strategies, as well as future research to explore the mechanisms underlying these complex dynamics.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

As part of our contribution to identifying the main determinants of the development of sustainable marketing (SM) in enterprises, we analysed the influence of cultural and political determinants on the development of sustainable marketing (SM) in industrial enterprises in Cameroon. To achieve this objective, this study highlighted the importance of these factors in the adoption of sustainable marketing practices by industrial enterprises in Cameroon. The results obtained through exploratory factor analysis, dependency tests, Pearson correlation, logistic regression model and linear regression model provide empirical evidence of the influence of cultural and political factors on the development of sustainable marketing (SM) in industrial enterprises in Cameroon. It is based on primary and secondary qualitative and quantitative data collected from a sample of 74 Cameroonian industrial enterprises in the Centre, Littoral and West regions in 2022. These findings have many practical implications. On the one hand, they highlight the importance of incorporating local cultural characteristics such as personal development, language and religion in the design and

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

implementation of sustainable marketing strategies. On the other hand, they also show that regulatory frameworks and standards, such as those set out by the Agency for Standards and Quality (ANOR), play an important and complex role since their mere presence does not necessarily guarantee the effective implementation of sustainable practices. These findings suggest that sustainable marketing strategies, to be truly effective, need to be differentiated and adapted to local cultural and political realities. The results also show that companies that take into account local cultural values and are sensitive to environmental policies are more likely to succeed in transitioning towards more responsible and sustainable marketing practices. These results suggest that state or Cameroonian authorities, as well as industrial companies, need to take action. At the government level, it is important for Cameroonian authorities to strengthen regulatory frameworks and standards for sustainable development and ensure that they are effectively implemented. Compliance with quality standards such as those set by ANOR has proven to be a positive for DMD. Regulators should therefore not only issue clear laws but also ensure that they are strictly applied and accepted by businesses. Cameroonian authorities should provide subsidies and incentives to businesses that adopt sustainable practices. The public needs to be aware of the benefits of sustainable marketing. Industrial companies need to incorporate local cultural values, such as self-realisation and language, into their sustainable marketing strategies. Companies also need to adapt their sustainable marketing strategies to local cultural and political characteristics. Finally, companies need to involve more stakeholders, including local communities, in the co-development of sustainable marketing strategies. This participatory approach may help increase the acceptance and effectiveness of sustainable initiatives by ensuring they are aligned with local needs and values. Although the statistical analyses used are robust, this study's focus on industrial companies in Cameroon limits the generalisability of the results to other regions and industries. The cultural and political characteristics of Cameroon may not be representative of other contexts. As a perspective for future research, it would be important to conduct comparative studies between different regions or countries to gain a deeper understanding of how cultural and political contexts affect sustainable marketing. Future research could focus on the influence of regional institutions, such as professional associations and industry associations, on the adoption of sustainable marketing practices. Exploring the influence of institutions may reveal additional avenues for promoting DSM.

REFERENCES

- 1) Aaker, D. A. (1996). Measuring brand equity across products and markets. *California management review*, 38(3).
- 2) Afshari, H., Agnihotri, S., Searcy, C., & Jaber, M. Y. (2022). Social sustainability indicators: A comprehensive review with application in the energy sector. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 31, 263-286
- 3) Ahmad, A. Mahmood, H. Han, A. Ariza-Montes, A. Vega-Munoz, ~ M.U. Din, Z. Ullah, (2021), Sustainability as a "new normal" for modern businesses: are smes of Pakistan ready to adopt it? *Sustainability*, 13 (4), 1944.
- 4) Ahmed, M.M. Asghar, M.N. Malik, K. Nawaz, (2020), Moving towards a sustainable environment: the dynamic linkage between natural resources, human capital, urbanization, economic growth, and ecological footprint in China, *Resour. Pol.* 67, 101677.
- 5) Alfoqahaa, S., & Safi, M. (2015). Factors Affecting the Adoption of Sustainable Marketing by Food industrial Companies in Palestine. *Jordan Journal of Business Administration*, 11(2).
- 6) Anderson Jr, W. T., & Cunningham, W. H. (1972). The socially conscious consumer. *Journal of marketing*, 36(3), 23-31.
- 7) Athwal, N., Wells, V. K., Carrigan, M., & Henninger, C. E. (2019). Sustainable luxury marketing: A synthesis and research agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 21(4), 405-426.
- 8) Bašan, L., Kapeš, J., & Brolich, L. (2021). Sustainable marketing factors: Impact on tourist satisfaction and perceived cultural tourism effects. *Ekonomski vjesnik: Review of Contemporary Entrepreneurship, Business, and Economic Issues*, 34(2), 385-400.
- 9) Blasco, D., Palau, R., Forgas, S., & Ferrer, B. (2012). An analysis of greenways from an economic perspective. *Tourism Planning & Development*, 9(1), 15-24.
- 10) Bonini, S. Gorner, "The Business of Sustainability", McKinsey & Company, 2011.
- 11) Bosson, E., Boolaky, M., & Gungaphul, M. (2016). The influence of national culture on marketing strategies in Africa. *Journal of Business Administration Research*, 5(2), 83-100.
- 12) Boubakary, B., Ngo Nken, I., & Donatienne Moskolai, D. (2024). Discovering the deep roots of corporate social responsibility in SMEs: An empirical exploration of the entrepreneurial fabric of Cameroon. *Review of Innovation and Competitiveness: A*

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Politic Context

- Journal of Economic and Social Research, 10(1), 7-30. Charter, M. (1992). Green marketing: The key to business survival. Pitman Publishing.
- 13) Coddington, W. (1993), Environmental Marketing Positive Strategies for Reaching the Green Consumer, McGraw-Hill Inc., New York.
 - 14) Crane, A., & Desmond, J. (2002). Sustainable marketing: Managing marketing in a greening world. Financial Times/Prentice Hall.
 - 15) D'Souza, C., Apaolaza, V., Hartmann, P., & Brouwer, A. R. (2021). Marketing for sustainability: Travellers' intentions to stay in green hotels. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 27(2), 187-202.
 - 16) D'Souza, C., Marjoribanks, T., Young, S., Sullivan Mort, G., Nanere, M., & John, J. J. (2019). Environmental management systems: an alternative marketing strategy for sustainability. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 27(5), 417-434.
 - 17) Dangelico, R. M., & Vocalelli, D. (2017). "Green Marketing": An analysis of definitions, strategy steps, and tools through a systematic review of the literature. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 165, 1263- 1279.
 - 18) Dawson, L. M. (1971). The crisis in marketing thought. *Business Horizons*, 14(4), 59-66.
 - 19) Dekhili, S., & Achabou, M. A. (2015). The influence of the country-of-origin ecological image on ecolabelled product evaluation: An experimental approach to the case of the European ecolabel. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 131, 89-106.
 - 20) Dekhili, S., Merle, A., & Ochs, A. (2021). Marketing durable. Pearson.
 - 21) Dekhili, S., Durif, F., & Merle, A. (2023). Sustainable marketing: Let's accelerate transformations!. *Recherche et Applications en Marketing (English Edition)*, 38(3), 2-4.
 - 22) Delmas, M. A., & Pekovic, S. (2018). Organizational configurations for sustainability and employee productivity: A qualitative comparative analysis approach. *Business & Society*, 57(1), 216-251.
 - 23) DiMaggio P.J. et Powell W.W. (1983). The Iron Cage Revisited : Institutional Isomorphism and Collective Rationality in Organizational Fields. *American Sociological Review*, vol. 48, p. 147-155.
 - 24) Eccles, R. G., & Serafeim, G. (2013). A tale of two stories: Sustainability and the quarterly earnings call. *Journal of Applied Corporate Finance*, 25(3), 8-19.
 - 25) Feldman, L. P. (1971). Marketing and social problems. *Journal of Marketing*, 35(1), 38-45.
 - 26) Fisk, G. (1973). Criteria for a Theory of Responsible Consumption. *Journal of Marketing*, 37(2), 32-40. Fisk, G. (1974). *Marketing and the Ecological Crisis*. Harper and Row, London.
 - 27) Font, X., & McCabe, S. (2019). Sustainability and marketing in tourism: Its contexts, paradoxes, approaches, challenges and potential. In *Marketing for Sustainable Tourism* (pp. 1-15). Routledge.
 - 28) Freeman, R. E. (1984). *Strategic Management : A Stakeholder Approach*. Pitman, Boston.
 - 29) Fuller, D. A. (1999). *Sustainable marketing: Building business with a triple bottom line*. McGraw-Hill.
 - 30) Gerus, E. D. (2013). Le phénomène de greenwashing et son impact sur les consommateurs: une étude multiculturelle (Doctoral dissertation, Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières).
 - 31) Gliszinski, D. J. (2007). Transformative higher education: A meaningful degree of understanding. *Journal of transformative education*, 5(4), 317-328.
 - 32) González-Benito, Ó. & Valenzuela-Gálvez, E. S., Garrido-Morgado, A., (2022). Boost your email marketing campaign! Emojis as visual stimuli to influence customer engagement. *Journal of research in interactive marketing*, 17(3), 337-352.
 - 33) Henion, K.E. (1976), *Ecological Marketing*, Grid Inc., Columbus.
 - 34) Henion, K.E. and Kinnear, T.C. (1976) *A Guide to Ecological Marketing*. Ecological Marketing.
 - 35) American Marketing Association, Columbus
 - 36) Hofstede, G. (1980). *Culture's Consequences : International Differences in Work-Related Values*. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications.
 - 37) Hofstede, G. (2011). Dimensionalizing cultures: The Hofstede model in context. *Online readings in psychology and culture*, 2(1), 8.
 - 38) Imed Zaiem, B. (2005). Influence de la communication externe environnementale sur l'image et le comportement du consommateur. Thèse de doctorat, Université Lumière Lyon 2.
 - 39) Jones, P., Clarke-Hill, C., Comfort, D., & Hillier, D. (2008). Marketing and sustainability. *Marketing intelligence & planning*,

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Politic Context

- 26(2), 123-130.
- 42) Kelley, P. J. (1971). Marketing's role in creating social change. *Journal of Marketing*, 35(1), 35-41. Kemper, C.M. Hall, P.W. Ballantine, (2019), Marketing and sustainability: business as usual or changing worldviews? *Sustainability*, 11 (3) 780.
- 43) Kemper, J. A., & Ballantine, P. W. (2019). What do we mean by sustainability marketing?. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 35(3-4), 277-309.
- 44) Kilbourne, (2006), The role of the dominant social paradigm in the quality of life/environmental interface, *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, 1 (1), 39-61.
- 45) Kilbourne, W.E. (1998), "Green Marketing: A Theoretical Perspective", *Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol.14 No. 6, pp. 641-655.
- 46) Kim, Y., Byeon, J., Jeong, Y., Choi, S., & Jung, S. P. (2023). Effective Policies Derived from Case analysis of Environmental Factors in ESG Management. *J Korean Soc Environ Eng*, 45(9), 371-387.
- 47) Kim, Y., Yun, S., Lee, J., & Ko, E. (2018). How consumer knowledge shapes green consumption: An empirical study on voluntary carbon offsetting. In *Social and environmental issues in advertising*, (pp. 33- 51). Routledge.
- 48) Kinnear, T. C., & Taylor, J. R. (1973) "The Effect of Ecological Concern on Brand Perceptions",
- 49) *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 10 No. 2, pp. 191-197.
- 50) Kinnear, T. C., Taylor, J. R., & Ahmed, S. A. (1974). Ecologically concerned consumers: who are they? Ecologically concerned consumers can be identified. *Journal of marketing*, 38(2), 20-24.
- 51) Kotler, P. (1972). A generic concept of marketing. *Journal of marketing*, 36(2), 46-54.
- 52) Kotler, P. (2011). Reinventing marketing to manage the environmental imperative. *Journal of marketing*, 75(4), 132-135.
- 53) Kumar, P. (2016). State of green marketing research over 25 years (1990-2014) literature survey and classification. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 34(1), 137-158.
- 54) Lazer William and Eugene J. Kelley. (1973). *Social marketing: perspectives and viewpoints*, ed. Business & Economics - 505 p
- 55) Lazer, W. (1969). Marketing and the institutionalization of science. *Science*, 163(3860), 299-305.
- 56) Lee, E., & Kim, G. (2022). Analysis of domestic and international green infrastructure research trends from the ESG perspective in South Korea. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(12), 7099.
- 57) Lee, J. H., Wood, J., & Kim, J. (2021). Tracing the trends in sustainability and social media research using topic modeling. *Sustainability*, 13(3), 1269.
- 58) Leisinger, K. (2015). Business needs to embrace sustainability targets. *Nature*, 528(7581), 165-165. Li, Z., Pan, Y., Yang, W., Ma, J., & Zhou, M. (2021). Effects of government subsidies on green technology investment and green marketing coordination of supply chain under the cap-and-trade mechanism. *Energy Economics*, 101, 105426.
- 59) Lim, W. M. (2016). A blueprint for sustainability marketing: Defining its conceptual boundaries for progress. *Marketing theory*, 16(2), 232-249.
- 60) Lin, Y. C., & Chang, C. C. A. (2012). Double standard: The role of environmental consciousness in green product usage. *Journal of Marketing*, 76(5), 125-134.
- 61) Lunde, M. B. (2018). Sustainability in marketing: A systematic review unifying 20 years of theoretical and substantive contributions (1997-2016). *AMS review*, 8(3), 85-110.
- 62) Manta, F., Campobasso, F., Tarulli, A., & Morrone, D. (2022). Showcasing green: how culture influences sustainable behavior in food eco-labeling. *British Food Journal*, 124(11), 3582-3594.
- 63) Marguerat, D. et Cestre, G. (2002). Le consommateur « vert » : attitude et comportement [version électronique]. Institut Universitaire de Management International (IUMI). Extrait le 09 avril 2010: http://www.hec.unil.ch/lcms_irrn/WP0211.pdf
- 64) Marshall, J. D. & Hankey, S. (2010). Impacts of urban form on future US passenger-vehicle greenhouse gas emissions. *Energy Policy*, 38(9), 4880-4887.
- 65) Matthes, J., & Wonneberger, A. (2014). The skeptical green consumer revisited: Testing the relationship between green consumerism and skepticism toward advertising. *Journal of advertising*, 43(2), 115-127.
- 66) Mattsson, L. G. (2016). Bridging gaps between policies for sustainable markets and market practices. *IMP Journal*, 10(2), 339-356.
- 67) MBIADJO Mimosette, F. F., & Paul, D. J. E. U. M. E. N. E. (2015). Factors explaining the adoption of mobile marketing in

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Politic Context

- Cameroon: Exploratory study on the use of SMS as method of transmission of social information. *African Journal of Marketing Management*, 7(2), 20-31.
- 68) Meng, J. (2015). Sustainability: a framework of typology based on efficiency and effectiveness. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 35(1), 84-98.
- 69) Menon, A., & Menon, A. (1997). Enviropreneurial Marketing Strategy: The Emergence of Corporate Environmentalism as Market Strategy. *Journal of Marketing*, 61, (1), pp. 51-67.
- 70) Merizrow, J. (2004). Learning to transform the self: the implications of connectivism for adult learning. In D. A.Roberts (Ed.), *Adult learning for the 21st century: a new future for education* (pp. 129-147). Jossey-Bass.
- 71) Mintu, A. T., & Lozada, G. A., (1993), Green Marketing Education: A Call for Action. *Marketing Education Review*. 3(3), pp17-23.
- 72) Mohd Suki, N., & Mohd Suki, N. (2015). Consumption values and consumer environmental concern regarding green products. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 22(3), 269- 278.
- 73) Nitcheu Tcheuffa, P. C., Kala Kamdjoug, J. R., & Fosso Wamba, S. (2020). Moderating effects of age and gender on social commerce adoption factors the Cameroonian context. *ICT for an Inclusive World: Industry 4.0–Towards the Smart Enterprise*, 263-274.
- 74) Noutsa Fobang, A., Fosso Wamba, S., & Kala Kamdjoug, J. R. (2019). Exploring factors affecting the adoption of HRIS in SMEs in a developing country: Evidence from Cameroon. *ICT for a Better Life and a Better World: The Impact of Information and Communication Technologies on Organizations and Society*, 281-295.
- 75) Oginni, O., & Omojowo, A. (2015). The implementation of sustainable business model among industries in Cameroon. *OIDA International Journal of Sustainable Development*, 8(11), 71-80.
- 76) Patel, Robert M. ; Castro, William C. ; Silva, Helder H. ; Nunes, José Mauro g. (2006). *comportement du consommateur et des études de marché*. 3ème. Éd., Rio de Janeiro : Editora FGV,
- 77) Peattie, K. (1995). *Environmental marketing management: Meeting the green challenge*.
- 78) Peattie, K., & Crane, A. (2005). Green marketing: Opportunity for corporate environmental sustainability and competitive advantage. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 21(5-6), 555-572.
- 79) Ray, S., & Nayak, L. (2023). Marketing sustainable fashion: trends and future directions. *Sustainability*, 15(7), 6202.
- 80) Sempels, C. et Vandercarnmen, M., (2009), *Oser le marketing durable concilier marketing et développement durable*. Paris: Pearson, 224 p.
- 81) Shen, D., Richards, J., & Liu, F. (2013). Consumers' awareness of sustainable fashion. *Marketing Management Journal*, 23(2), 134-147.
- 82) Sheth, J. N., & Parvatiyar, A. (1995). Sustainable marketing: A new perspective. *Journal of Macromarketing*, 15(1), 1-16.
- 83) Sisaye, S. (2021). The influence of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) on the development of voluntary sustainability accounting reporting rules. *Journal of Business and Socio-economic Development*, 1(1), 5-23.
- 84) Spence Martine, Jouhaina Ben Boubaker Gherib, (2010). Sustainable Entrepreneurship: Is Entrepreneurial will Enough? A North–South Comparison. *Journal of Business Ethics.*, 99:335–367 Spence, A. M. (2005). *PME et développement durable: Menace ou opportunité?* Ottawa: École de gestion, 18 p.
- 85) Spence, M., Biwolé, V.O. et Gherib.,J.B.B, (2007), *Une étude exploratoire des fondements du degré d'engagement des PME dans le développement durable*. Ottawa: École de gestion, 18 p.
- 86) Stamm KR, Clark F and Eblacas PR , (2000), « Mass communication and public understanding of environmental problems: The case of global warming », *Public Understanding of Science*, 9(3): 219–237.
- 87) Swim, J., Stern, P., & Becker, L. (2009). An integrative theoretical framework for understanding psychological barriers to climate change mitigation and adaptation. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 29(4), 350-363.
- 88) Stubbs, R., & Cocklin, M. (2008). Greening supply chains: the "how" and "why" of linking environmental strategy to supplier selection. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 16(1), 56-65.
- 89) Tagne, J. S., & Evou, J. P. (2020). Cultural diversity and performance of Cameroonian companies. In *Cultural factors and performance in 21st century businesses* (pp. 144-163). IGI Global.
- 90) Tajfel, H. (1972). La catégorisation sociale. In S. Moscovici (Ed.), *Introduction à la psychologie sociale* (Vol. 1, pp. 272-

Development of Sustainable Marketing Within Industrial Businesses: The Decisive Influence of the Cultural and Political Context

302). Paris: Larousse.4

- 91) Trivedi, K., Trivedi, P., & Goswami, V. (2018). Sustainable marketing strategies: Creating business value by meeting consumer expectation. *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences (IJMESS)*, 7(2), 186-205.
- 92) Van Dam, Y. K., & Apeldoorn, P. A. (1996). Sustainable marketing. *Journal of macromarketing*, 16(2), 45-56.
- 93) Varadarajan, P. R., & Menon, A. (1988). Environmental marketing: A managerial perspective. *Journal of Marketing*, 52(4), 64-74.
- 94) Yildiz Çankaya, S., & Sezen, B. (2019). Effects of green supply chain management practices on sustainability performance. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 30(1), 98-121.

Appendix :

Table 1: Relationship between cultural and political factors and the development of sustainable marketing

practical level of sustainable marketing

Items	value Khi-2	probability	SignificantDependence
Cultural (values and beliefs)			
C1 : Personal development	68.84	0.000	yes
C2: Belief in the usefulness of sustainable development	100.65	0.000	yes
C3 : Religion	67.05	0.000	yes
C4 : Language	56.32	0.000	yes
C5: Membership of an ethnic group	60.34	0.000	yes
Politics (laws and standards)			
P1: Compliance with laws or standards	88.40	0.000	yes
P2: Products and/or services subject to regulation	29.52	0.000	yes
P3: Compliance with ANOR standards and quality	32.61	0.000	yes

Source: author based on our results

Table 2. Pearson Correlation matrix of variables

Items	Correlation Pearson	probability
C1 : Personal development	0.706***	0.000
C2: Belief in the usefulness of sustainable development	0.363***	0.001
C3 : Religion	0.455***	0.000
C4 : Language	0.652***	0.000
C5: Membership of an ethnic group	0.326***	0.005
P1: Compliance with laws or standards	0.128	0.278
P2: Products and/or services subject to regulation	0.146	0.214
P3: Compliance with ANOR standards and quality	0.384***	0.000

***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1. N =74

Table 3 : Analysis of variance test (ANOVA test) on cultural and political factors

DSM	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7,332	2	3,666	4,502	0,014
Within Groups	57,816	71	0,814		
Total	65,149	73			

Source: author based on estimate